

Ghosted Rooms: A Novel Grid-Based Puzzle with Unique Room Partitioning

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Website: <https://ghosted-rooms.com>

Abstract

Ghosted Rooms is a logic puzzle in which a grid filled with numbers must be partitioned into rooms of equal area. The allowed room shapes are predefined, and each puzzle has exactly one valid solution. Within every room, all possible numbers appear once and only once.

Eight-Cell Rooms

Certain puzzles use eight-cell rooms. The possible shapes can appear rotated or mirrored (6 distinct variants).

Figure 1. Possible shapes of eight-cell rooms

Figure 2. Sample puzzle with eight-cell rooms.

1	4	6		7	8	3	2	1	6	7	6	1	3
	8	5	1	2	6	4	5	8		4	8	7	
2	7	3	8	7	6		5	3	5	2	4	5	4
	2	1	4	2	7	8		1	6	1	8		3
4	6	1	6		1	5	7	2		7	5	6	2
5	7	3	4	6	3	2	4	8	2	8	7	8	4
8	4	7	8	5	7		1	6		1	5	2	1
2	6	5		1	3	3	7	5	7	4	8	6	7
	3		2	3	7	4	8	2	8		1		4
	5	4	6	5	8	6	2	5	3	7	6	6	
6	1	4	5	4		3	6		4	3	8	5	4
7	8	2	8	6	7	2	8	5	2	7	3	1	7

Figure 3. Solution to the sample puzzle.

1	4	6	5	7	8	3	2	1	6	7	6	1	3
3	8	5	1	2	6	4	5	8	3	4	8	7	2
2	7	3	8	7	6	4	5	3	5	2	4	5	4
8	2	1	4	2	7	8	6	1	6	1	8	1	3
4	6	1	6	5	1	5	7	2	3	7	5	6	2
5	7	3	4	6	3	2	4	8	2	8	7	8	4
8	4	7	8	5	7	5	1	6	3	1	5	2	1
2	6	5	2	1	3	3	7	5	7	4	8	6	7
1	3	1	2	3	7	4	8	2	8	4	1	3	4
3	5	4	6	5	8	6	2	5	3	7	6	6	2
6	1	4	5	4	1	3	6	1	4	3	8	5	4
7	8	2	8	6	7	2	8	5	2	7	3	1	7

Ten-Cell Rooms

Other puzzles use ten-cell rooms. These shapes can also appear rotated or mirrored (18 distinct variants).

Figure 4. Possible shapes of ten-cell rooms

Figure 5. Sample puzzle with ten-cell rooms.

9	0	3	5	8	1	2	0	1	4	1	5	7	0	3
1		6	4	6	2	3	6		8	6	2	3	4	9
7	5	8	7	4	9		9	5	8	0		9	1	8
4	8	1	9	5	7	3	6	1	6	3	0	8		2
2	3	8	6	5	9	0	3	4	5	2	8	9	7	5
6	0	2	7	4	5	8	7		4	4	1	3	6	
1			3		0	7	3	9	1	9	0		4	2
7	2	9	0	5	2	9	0	2		0	6	5		5
5	3	4		6	3	1	4	7	8	3	7	3	1	0
8	6	8	7	8	1	6		8	6	1	0	7	7	8
3		0	4	3	9	2	5	8	4	2	5	6	2	9
1	9	6	2		0	1	4	6	7	9	8	1		3

Figure 6. Solution to the sample puzzle.

9	0	3	5	8	1	2	0	1	4	1	5	7	0	3
1	2	6	4	6	2	3	6	7	8	6	2	3	4	9
7	5	8	7	4	9	0	9	5	8	0	4	9	1	8
4	8	1	9	5	7	3	6	1	6	3	0	8	6	2
2	3	8	6	5	9	0	3	4	5	2	8	9	7	5
6	0	2	7	4	5	8	7	2	7	4	4	1	3	6
1	9	0	3	4	0	7	3	9	1	9	0	2	4	2
7	2	9	0	5	2	9	0	2	5	0	6	5	9	5
5	3	4	1	6	3	1	4	7	8	3	7	3	1	0
8	6	8	7	8	1	6	5	8	6	1	0	7	7	8
3	5	0	4	3	9	2	5	8	4	2	5	6	2	9
1	9	6	2	7	0	1	4	6	7	9	8	1	4	3

Grid Variations

Variant	Description
Basic	Every cell is filled with the correct numbers.
Missing number	Each room is missing one number.
Erroneous number	Each room contains one duplicated number; either duplicate may be corrected.
Combined variants	Any combination of the above may appear.

Further Variations

- The grid, rooms, and their sizes may vary arbitrarily.
- Instead of numbers, letters or other symbols may be used.
- The grid itself may be irregular (not necessarily rectangular).
- The grid may include forbidden cells that do not belong to the puzzle and remain empty. Such cells are usually shown in black, similar to crossword puzzles.

Keywords

Puzzle · Logic game · Recreational mathematics · Grid partitioning · Room shapes

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